
Does a relationship exist between GLOBE Study Leadership Behaviors and GDP per Capita and Happiness Indicators?

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Received on: July 13, 2022; revised on July 21, 2022; published on July 23, 2022

Abstract

This article expands the GLOBE Study to determine if a relationship exists between leadership behaviors, economic performance, and well-being indicators (happiness). The Globe Study is based on the 62 countries that formed the basis of the original foundational work. Economic performance is defined as Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per Capita and well-being as the Happiness indicator that is a subjective measure gathered by a country. It does not focus on the cultural aspects of leadership but rather on the leadership behaviors that help promote economic performance and social well-being as measured by happiness indicators by country.

The results show that leadership behaviors are not strong predictors of GDP per Capita. In other words, no specific leadership behavior is related to GDP per Capita growth for both developed and developing countries. However, the Type of Country and Low Corruption Indicators are consistent predictors of GDP per Capita. Furthermore, Low Corruption Indicators, Life Expectancy, and Participative Leadership are predictors of happiness for a given country.

Keywords: Leadership, Leadership Behaviors, GLOBE Study, GDP per Capita, Happiness Indicators

Introduction

Leadership as a study has a long history, Plutarch the ancient Greek biographer and essayist portrayed the leader as someone who is governed by “reason” and “virtue” (Beneker, 2019). Since ancient times, leadership has been described as a rare and sought-after commodity, a critical factor in society, and a key component of social progress (Northouse P. G., 2010). Machiavelli, in the Middle Ages (Machiavelli, 1469) described the study (of leadership) as: “The possession none that I so much prize and esteem as a knowledge of the actions of great men.” Today, a commonly used definition “is that of a process whereby an individual influences a group to achieve a common goal” (Northouse P. G., 2010). However, something has made leadership both ubiquitous and scarce and despite so much training offered there seems to be a colossal failure in the practice (Aboujaoude, 2021). Early Leadership Theory identified the trait approach as one of the first systematic ways of studying what made some individuals great leaders. As a result, and after a long journey, a few attributes were identified to be major traits: intelligence, integrity, self-confidence, determination, and sociability (Northouse P. G., 2010). A consensus later emerged amongst researchers on five factors that make up a relevant personality: neuroticism, extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness (Goldberg, 1990). This model is described as the “Big Five” personality factors and is commonly utilized by scholars. Then Ohio State researchers believed that studying leadership as a personality trait was not productive; therefore, decided to analyze how leaders acted when leading a group or organization. The research identified two types of leader behaviors (Stogdil, 1974) that are fundamental: task and relationship-oriented behaviors (Northouse P. G., 2010). In succeeding years, the Global Leadership and Organizational Behavior Effectiveness (GLOBE) Study (House, 2004) defined six key leadership behaviors: Performance Oriented, Team Oriented, Participative, Humane Oriented, Autonomous, and Self-Protective. These leader behaviors were utilized to evaluate the desired leadership behavioral preferences selected by each culture in the study. Executives tend to lead more successfully when they behave in manners that are endorsed and expected by a given culture (Dorfman, Javidan, & al., 2012). Every culture has its leadership preferences that determine what leadership behaviors to emphasize or de-emphasize and which are commonly accepted or rejected. Other studies expand on the definition of leaders and what characterizes a global leader (Reiche, Bird, Mendenhall, & Osland, 2015) to provide additional context and understanding. Effective global leaders generally have an open mindset, possess the ability to deal with ambiguity, and demonstrate cultural adaptability and flexibility (Javidan, Luque, Dorfman, & House, 2006). In addition, they tend to integrate and balance task-oriented “global complexity” and relationship-oriented “global continuity” as components of leadership (Dorfman, Javidan, & al., 2012). In the current social context when business and government leadership legitimacy is being questioned (Nohira & Khurana, 2010, p. 3), societies around the world are now in desperate need of better leadership and results. Particularly when many key political figures and national leaders (in multiple disciplines) currently behave and communicate in disruptive and self-protective ways. The social implications are not fully understood of this kind of behavior nor their impact on a nation’s economic performance or its social well-being. Creating the need to research leadership behavior(s) in a more focused manner and from the perspective that leadership is best assessed by its results in two important factors: economic performance and social well-being (or happiness indicators).

The research presented herein is a quantitative relational study based on the GLOBE Study key leadership behavior(s) and their measures at a national level. The research seeks to identify whether a relationship exists between leadership behaviors, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita,

and overall happiness indicators (as a measure of social well-being by country).

1.1 Background

The GLOBE is a multi-year effort based on a quantitative survey of national and organizational cultures and the assessment of effective leadership attributes in 62 countries around the world (House, 2004). Robert J. House (House, 2004) was fundamental to the research which he initiated by studying the universality of charismatic leadership across diverse societies. It started during the 1990s and was based on a survey of 17,000 mid-level managers in several industries across 62 countries (House, Hanges, Javidan, Dorfman, & Gupta, Culture, Leadership, and Organizations, 2004). According to the study, leadership is measured by the quality of leaders an organization has and by their ability to deliver results.

The GLOBE’s six key leadership behaviors which help frame the research are Performance Oriented (Charismatic/value-based), Team Oriented, Participative, Humane, Autonomous, and Self Protective. In addition, key cultural dimensions identified are Performance Orientation, Uncertainty Avoidance, In-Group Collectivism, Power Distance, Gender Egalitarianism, Humane Orientation, Institutional Collectivism, Future Orientation, and Assertiveness. These leadership and cultural dimensions are associated with the different cultural clusters around the world. The countries which were analyzed resulted in ten cultural clusters defined as Nordic, Anglo, Germanic, Latin European, African, Eastern European, Middle Eastern, Confucian, Southeast Asian, and Latin American.

1.2 Problem Statement

Leadership as highlighted by Northouse is a valued and rare commodity in society (Northouse, 2016) and more so when humanity continues to struggle with issues like corruption, failing economies, political instability, social unrest, and social inequality. There are signs of all types of war e.g.: in trade, currency, drugs, poverty, and military to name a few. A general malaise has overtaken the political systems and social discourse in the U.S. (Ferguson, 2013) and around the world. There is an abundance of disruptive and self-protective leaders whose behavior(s) are detrimental to healthy national dialogue(s) that are much needed to solve critical world issues.

Leadership is key to properly guide society in ways that are both transformative and ways that increase human potential. An underlying perspective of this research is that leaders and the behaviors they display may ultimately affect how society performs economically and how it creates or destroys social well-being (measured through happiness indicators). In general, the social implications of disruptive and inappropriate leadership behaviors have not been fully studied on a fundamental level nor have their relationship to key economic performance and national happiness measures. This research is a quantitative relational study to determine if there is a relationship between leadership behaviors and a nation’s economic performance and national happiness indicators. If a relationship is determined, then additional research is warranted to determine causation.

2 Methods

This study followed a quantitative approach allowing researchers the use of correlational statistics to explain and quantify the degree of relationship between two or more variables (Cozby & Bates, 2012; Patton, 2015). Quantitative approaches aim to measure variables or data numerically and objectively and make use of statistical techniques to analyze the underlying relationship between and among these variables or data (Bryman, 2012). Furthermore, quantitative approaches deduce insights from numerically measured and statistically tested data in the hope of generalizing the

findings to a larger population (Allwood, 2012). This study measured the variables (leadership behaviors, GDP per capita, and various control variables) numerically using reported data gathered from multiple databases, which will then be analyzed using statistical analysis to address the research questions and hypotheses.

H01: There is no relationship between Leadership Behaviors (Performance Oriented (Charismatic/value-based), Team Oriented, Participative, Humane, Autonomous, and Self Protective) per the Globe Study and a country's GDP per capita when controlling for the Type of Country, Corruption Indicator, Intelligence Quotient, Gini Coefficient, and Labor Market Participation.

H02: There is no relationship between Leadership Behaviors (Performance Oriented (Charismatic/value-based), Team Oriented, Participative, Humane, Autonomous, and Self Protective) per the Globe Study and a country's Happiness Indicators when controlling for Type of Country, Corruption Indicator, Life Expectancy, and Gini Coefficient.

2.1 Population and Sample Selection

The target population for this study is the countries included in the GLOBE Study (House, 2004). Then 62 countries were selected and divided into 10 cultural clusters: Nordic, Anglo, Germanic, Latin European, African, Eastern European, Middle Eastern, Confucian, Southeast Asian, and Latin American. The full list of the 62 countries is in Appendix A. Provided that all countries will be included in the study, no sampling is needed anymore.

2.2 Data Collection

The data to be used is based on the reports from Globe Study (House et al., 2014). Specifically, the data was collected from various published reports where all needed data for the study variables are present.

2.3 Operationalization of Variables

Independent variable. The independent variable for this study is the Globe Study's leadership behaviors. There are six leadership behaviors and the measurement and description of each are discussed below.

1. Performance-oriented (Charismatic/value-based) - A leadership style that stresses high standards, decisiveness, and innovation, seeks to inspire people around a vision, creates a passion among them to perform, and does so by firmly holding on to core values. This is measured in continuous form.
2. Team-oriented - A leadership style that encourages input from others in decision making and implementation, it emphasizes delegation and equality. This will be measured in continuous form.
3. Participative - A style of leadership in which all members of the organization work together to make decisions. This will be measured in continuous form.
4. Humane - A leadership style that stresses compassion and generosity, patience, support, and concern for the well-being of others. This will be measured in continuous form.
5. Autonomous - A leadership style that is characterized by an independent, individualistic, and self-centered approach to leadership. This will be measured in continuous form.
6. Self-Protective - A leadership style that emphasizes procedural, status-conscious, and 'face-saving' behaviors and focuses on the safety and security of the individual and the group. This will be measured in continuous form.

Dependent variables. There are two dependent variables for this study – GDP per capita and happiness indicator.

1. GDP per capita - GDP per head calculated as the aggregate of production (GDP) divided by the population size (Nations, 2019). Other sources define GDP as the market value of final goods and services produced in each country (or other areas) during a given period and divided by the population size to obtain the GDP per capita. It is intended to measure an economy's production (Lemieux, 2016-2017) and income on an individual basis.
2. Happiness indicator - A measure of well-being by country World Bank and CIA Factbook in support of UN high-level objectives that gauge the happiness of a country by how their citizens perceive themselves.

Independent Control variables. There are six control variables, and the descriptions are discussed below.

1. Type of country – A dichotomous variable that refers to the level of national development of a country. A country is either developed or developing.
2. Corruption perception index – A continuous variable that refers to the perceived levels of public sector corruption, as determined by expert assessments and opinion surveys for each country.
3. Intelligence quotient – A continuous variable that indicates the apparent average relative intelligence (IQ) of a nation.
4. Life expectancy – A continuous variable that indicates the number of years on average a person will live in a country.
5. Gini coefficient – A continuous variable that represents income inequality or wealth inequality within a nation.
6. Labor market participation – A continuous variable that indicates the percentage of people in the labor market for a country.

2.4 Data Analysis Plan

The data plan included inferential statistical analyses, specifically multiple linear regression analysis, to examine the relationship between the independent variable leadership behavior and the dependent variables of GDP per capita and happiness indicators in the presence of several control variables. Regression analysis serves three purposes: description, control, and prediction (Nimon & Reio, 2011). The research design is a non-experimental study because there are no random assignment, manipulation, experimental, or control groups. Multiple regression analyses were conducted since there are multiple continuous independent and dependent variables. The study attempted to explore relationships and prediction, and explain the variance in R-squared, and R-Squared change. Furthermore, for those significant continuous variables, the beta weights which are the standardized slope, the partial correlation, and the scatterplot are provided.

There was a significant categorical variable with only two values (dichotomous) for which t-tests will be evaluated. Scheffe's posthoc test to find differences between group means was not needed at this time. Finally, a significance level of $p < .05$ is used based on the social science default number. Hypothesis one (research question one) had a regression equation with the six leadership behaviors as the independent variable, five control variables, and GDP per capita as the dependent variable. Hypothesis two (research question two) had a regression equation with six leadership behaviors as the independent variable, four control variables, and Happiness Indicators as the dependent variable. Since multiple linear regression analysis is considered a parametric test, therefore, certain assumptions must be met first before they can be used. There are four assumptions of parametric tests, and these include: (a) normality, (b) homogeneity of variance, (c) linearity, and (d) independence (Sedgwick, 2015). Hypothesis testing

was done on all analyses with a 0.05 level of significance (Weakliem, 2016).

2.5 Reliability and Validity

Given that the proposed research study is utilizing a non-experimental research design, there are several considerations for the internal and external validity of the study. That is, non-experimental designs are more susceptible to threats to validity (Wickens & Kappel, 2014). With a non-experimental design, there is little control of threats to validity since the design lacks manipulation of the independent variable and simply reveals group differences from pre-existing groups (Lohmeier, 2010). Nevertheless, it is important to note the types of threats to the validity of non-experimental designs.

3 Results

Multiple regression analysis was employed to find relationships between more than one independent and dependent variable.

3.1 Null Hypothesis (H01)

Multiple regression analysis for the null hypothesis was structured as follows. Block 1 represented a Stepwise Method which produces an efficient model, as each variable is considered independently used for the independent control variables defined as Type of Country, Corruption Indicators, Intelligent Quotient, Gini Coefficient, and Labor Market Participation. Furthermore, the dependent variable is identified for the null hypothesis one, as GDP per Capita.

The Block method for representing the regression model allows the regression analysis to explain as much variability as possible for the independent control variables, then the leadership behaviors are entered into the model to determine if they also contribute. The leadership behaviors are six from the GLOBE Study defined as Performance, Team, Participative, Humane Orientation, Autonomous, and Self-Protective Leadership.

H01: There is no relationship between Leadership Behaviors (Performance Oriented (Charismatic/value-based), Team Oriented, Participative, Humane, Autonomous, and Self Protective) per the Globe Study and a country's GDP per capita when controlling for the Type of Country, Corruption Indicator, Intelligence Quotient, Gini Coefficient, and Labor Market Participation.

Table A Results
Model Summary for H01

H01 Model Summary							
Mod	R	R Square	R Square Change	Beta	df 1	df 2	Sig. F Change
1	.886 ^a	0.786		0.616	1	56	0.000
2	.914 ^b	0.835	0.049		1	55	0.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), Corruption Index							
b. Predictors: (Constant), Corruption Index, Type of Country							

Table A provides the multiple regression results of the independent variables on the dependent variable of GDP per Capita. The findings show that Corruption Indicators (Index) and Type of Country were significant predictors of GDP per Capita. **The stated hypothesis H01 is accepted since there is no relationship between leadership behaviors and GDP**

per Capita. There is, however, a relationship between the Corruption Index explained by 78.6% of the variance ($R^2 = .786, \beta = .616, p < .05$).

Figure A shows the independent control variable Corruption Index for the GLOBE Study countries in a scatterplot diagram.

Figure A – GDP per Capita and Corruption Index (Indicator)

The Corruption Index is an inverse relationship, the higher the score the **less corrupt a country is** and the greater the GDP per Capita. The Type of Country accounted for an additional 4.9% of the variance ($\Delta R^2 = .049, p < .05$) in predicting GDP per Capita. Figure B below shows the Type of Country and GDP per Capita by developed and developing countries.

The first stated hypothesis was not rejected since there is no relationship between leadership behaviors and GDP per Capita. There was, however, a relationship of the Corruption Index explained by 78.6% of the variance. The Corruption Index is an inverse relationship, the higher the score the less corrupt a country is and the greater the GDP per Capita. The Type of Country accounted for an additional 4.9% of the variance in predicting GDP per Capita.

3.2 Null Hypothesis (H02)

Multiple regression analysis for null hypothesis two was structured as H01, where Block 1 represents a Stepwise Method used for the independent control variables defined as Type of Country, Corruption Indicators, Life Expectancy, and Gini Coefficient with the dependent variable Happiness Indicator.

H02: There is no relationship between Leadership Behaviors (Performance Oriented (Charismatic/value-based), Team Oriented, Participative, Humane, Autonomous, and Self Protective) per the Globe Study and a country's Happiness Indicators when controlling for Type of Country, Corruption Indicator, Life Expectancy, and Gini Coefficient.

Table B Results
Model Summary for H02

H02 Model Summary								
Mod	R	R Square	R Square Change	Beta	Partial Correlation	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.702 ^a	0.492		0.257		1	56	0.000
2	.753 ^b	0.568	0.076	0.427	0.462	1	55	0.003
3	.808 ^c	0.652	0.085	0.329	0.442	1	54	0.001
a. Predictors: (Constant), Corruption Index								

b. Predictors: (Constant), Corruption Index, Life Expectancy
c. Predictors: (Constant), Corruption Index, Life Expectancy, Participative

Table B provides the multiple regression results of the independent variables on the dependent variable of the Happiness Indicator. The findings indicate that Corruption Indicators (Index), Life Expectancy, and Participative leadership behaviors were significant predictors of Happiness Indicators. The stated hypothesis H02 is rejected since a relationship exists between leadership behaviors, Corruption Index, Life Expectancy, and Happiness Indicators. The Corruption Index explains by 49.2% of the variance ($R^2 = .492$, $\beta = .257$, $p < .05$). Figure B shows the scatterplot diagram of the independent variable Happiness Indicators and the Control Variable Corruption Index.

Figure B – Happiness Indicators and Corruption Index

The Corruption Index is an inverse relationship, the higher the score the *less corrupt a country is*, and the greater Happiness is perceived and reflected in the scores by the country. Life Expectancy accounted for an additional 7.6% of the variance ($\Delta R^2 = .076$, $\beta = .427$, $r_p = .442$, $p < .05$) in predicting Happiness Indicators. Participative leadership behaviors accounted for an additional 8.5% of the variance ($\Delta R^2 = .076$, $\beta = .427$, $r_p = .442$, $p < .05$) in predicting Happiness Indicators.

The second stated hypothesis was rejected since a relationship exists between leadership behaviors, Corruption Index, Life Expectancy, and Happiness Indicators. The Corruption Index explained 49.2% of the variance. Additionally, the Corruption Index is an inverse relationship, the higher the score the less corrupt a country is, and the greater Happiness is perceived and reflected in the scores by country. Life Expectancy accounted for an additional 7.6% of the variance in predicting Happiness Indicators Participative leadership behaviors accounted for an additional 8.5% of the variance in predicting Happiness Indicators.

4 Discussion

4.1 Overview

The purpose of this research is to uncover new patterns and relationships between leader behaviors, and economic and happiness indicators but also to confirm their significance to society and to leadership as a discipline. The research was designed to expand the knowledge of leadership beyond

cultural dimensions from the GLOBE Study. As the study mainly focused on leader behaviors, economic performance (task orientation), and happiness (relationship orientation) to uncover potential associations. The research explored the relationship between Leadership Behaviors (Performance Oriented (Charismatic/value-based), Team Oriented, Participative, Humane, Autonomous, and Self-Protective) per GLOBE and a country’s GDP per capita when controlling for type of country, corruption indicators, intelligence quotient, life expectancy, Gini coefficient, and labor market participation. And the relationship between Leadership Behaviors (Performance Oriented (Charismatic/value-based), Team Oriented, Participative, Humane, Autonomous, and Self-Protective) per GLOBE and a country’s Happiness Indicators when controlling for type of country, corruption indicators, life expectancy, and Gini coefficient.

4.2 Implications and Application

Findings from this study have many implications and applications for practicing leaders in a range of contexts and settings. The results of the research show that a single Leadership Behavior (e.g., Performance Oriented) is not a predictor of growth in GDP per Capita. However, Corruption and the Type of Country are important factors in predicting GDP per Capita. The result may imply that if a country seeks improvements in its general economic well-being that it must pay attention to corruption. Furthermore, the Type of Country is a predictor for GDP per Capita given that productivity levels in advanced countries are much higher, and the existence of larger consumer markets, legal frameworks, and financial institutions foster growth and entrepreneurship.

The social well-being results reflected in the Happiness Indicators show that Corruption, Life Expectancy, and Participative Leadership Behaviors are predictors. Corruption degrades the social fabric and degenerates a society into base instincts that weigh heavy on individual and social Happiness. In addition, to no surprise Life Expectancy is an important predictor of Happiness Indicators as these rely on the quality of life, health care, and positive family, community, and social interactions. Furthermore, a society that seeks the well-being of its members should rely more on Participative Leadership Behaviors to impact overall Happiness. An interesting finding that supports efforts to boost democratic processes around the world, reduce populous rhetoric, balance nationalistic discourse, and resist autocratic tendencies and regimes.

4.3 Limitations of Findings

Although this study is believed to make a significant contribution to the literature and understanding of factors like the influence of leadership behaviors on economics and public happiness, some limitations were present and require consideration. First, the research was based on the GLOBE Study which due to the COVID-19 pandemic has not updated its data because it is difficult to find data collectors. Recent results date back to 2014 in Strategic Leadership Across Cultures (House, Dorfman, Javidan, Hanges, & Sully de Luque, 2014); however, a few studies from Eastern Europe continue to validate GLOBE Study results and the “stickiness” of Leadership Behaviors and their value (Maczynski, Sulkowski, & Chmielecki, 2014).

5 Suggestions for Future Research

This study has provided an important area to further research by decoupling the study of leadership and Leadership Behaviors from culture and the GLOBE Study’s cultural dimensions. This is important because Leadership Behaviors can be also linked to other objectives deemed important by society. Future research is needed that draws on primary data so that confounding and extraneous variables can be controlled. Non-correlational research, such as longitudinal or time series data, may also be beneficial

in demonstrating how trends related to leadership, economics, and happiness change over time. It would also be interesting to examine how major public health or political events, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, have influenced leadership styles and their influences on the population. Each of these topics would offer important implications for understanding population health and informing public leaders in the development of policy.

6 Conclusion

The findings show that a less corrupt environment fosters “trust” which in turn may facilitate business, investment, entrepreneurship, and economic growth (GDP per Capita). In addition, the Type of Country is associated with greater GDP per Capita for developed countries. This is due possibly to better infrastructures, larger consumer and financial markets, higher purchasing power, effective legal systems, strong institutions, and governments that foment economic growth, entrepreneurship, “fairness” and “transparency” all of which may result in higher GDP per Capita.

However, no single leadership behavior was associated with GDP per Capita, and no significant relationship was identified. This does not mean that there is an absence of leadership behaviors but rather a combination of which may become more effective instruments for advanced and developing countries.

Results from this study showed that corruption is also associated with Happiness as it may promote social discord, instability, a lack of cohesiveness, and undermines “trust” all of which are related to well-being and overall Happiness. Lower Corruption discourages the abuse of public office for private gain, social marginalization, inequality, and discord reducing social tension. It is evident that a more corrupt leadership style, such as an autocratic one, is associated with lower levels of happiness based on the potential for it to create a state of social discord.

The study also found that there is a leadership behavior that is a positive predictor of Happiness scores, this leadership behavior is Participative Leadership. Participative Leadership behaviors are demonstrated by sharing power, control, and decision-making with other members of society. Furthermore, Participative Leadership may increase community involvement and accountability as the basis and foundation of a strong democratic system.

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